

EVALUATION OF THERMAL SHOCK FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF CERAMIC PARTICULATE-FILLED EPOXY RESIN

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ABSTRACTS

Thermal shock test was conducted on some ceramic particulate filled epoxies and thermal shock fracture toughness was evaluated based on fracture mechanics. The effect of filler content on thermal shock resistance was shown differently by the used fillers. From SEM observation, the fracture mechanisms were depended on strength of the interface and the filled particulate itself. Stress near crack tip field in the composite was analyzed with FEM. An influence of the debonding interface was discussed analytically and experimentally. Thermal shock fracture toughness of these composites were evaluated and compared with general fracture toughness.

INTRODUCTION

Ceramic particulate-filled epoxy resin is used for high performance insulating materials in electric and electronic fields. In application of particulate-filled epoxy composites for such fields, high reliability for thermal shock is required. Fracture by thermal shock is a complex phenomena because it is greatly affected by the geometry and the size of body which is applied thermal shock, the thermal and mechanical properties of material, and so forth.

In our previous studies, we reported the thermal shock resistance of neat epoxy resin and toughened epoxy with soft [1,2] and hard second phase [3-5] on the basis of our proposed thermal shock test and evaluation methods [2,6,7]. In the case of neat epoxy resins, fracture toughness obtained by thermal shock test was the same with that obtained by mechanical tests, such as bending or tensile tests. On the other hand, in the case of particulate filled composites, it was found that thermal shock fracture toughness value was not necessarily the same with mechanical value.

In this paper, the evaluation method of thermal shock resistance and thermal shock fracture toughness are discussed. The effect of debonding matrix / filler interface on thermal shock resistance and fracture toughness is studied from morphological and analytical viewpoint.

EXPERIMENTAL

(a) Materials

Materials used in this study were ceramic particulate filled epoxy composites. Two types of matrix resin were used. One of them was a mixture of alicyclic epoxy of epoxy equivalent 157, bisphenol A type epoxy of epoxy equivalent 370-435 and phthalic anhydride as a hardener. The weight ratio of resins and hardener was 1 : 9 : 3. The other matrix was bisphenol A type epoxy of epoxy equivalent 185-195 cured with 86 phr of methyl-hexahydro-phthalic anhydride. The former matrix was used for composites filled with angular shaped particulate, and the latter was used for composites filled with spherical particulate.

Alumina, silica, silicon carbide and silicon nitride were used as angular shaped fillers. These fillers have almost the same particle size distribution without any surface treatment (as received). In order to investigate the effect of filler content V_f on thermal shock resistance, V_f was varied from 0 to 45%. Globe-shaped alumina and glass beads were also used as fillers. In the case of spherical alumina, filler finished with silane coupling agent was also used for comparison with the filler as received. The physical and mechanical properties of these test materials were obtained experimentally.

(b) Testing & Evaluating Method

The mechanical fracture toughness is determined with single edge notched beam specimen loaded in three point bending [3]. The K_{Ic} value is given by

$$K_{Ic} = \frac{3 \{ 1.99 - \zeta (1 - \zeta) (2.15 - 3.93\zeta + 2.7\zeta^2) \} P S \sqrt{c}}{2(1 + 2\zeta)(1 - \zeta)^{3/2} B W^2} \quad \dots (1)$$

where P is maximum bending load, S is span, c is notch length, B is specimen thickness, W is specimen depth and $\zeta = c/W$.

Thermal shock tests are conducted with same method described in our previous papers [2,6,7], i.e. using sharp notched disk type specimen of 60 mm diameter and 10 mm thickness, shown in Fig.1. At first the specimen is heated in high temperature air bath with two balsa heat insulators attached on both flat sides of the specimen. Then the specimen is quickly put into the cooling bath, which causes only lateral heat transfer. After 5 minutes cooling, the specimen is checked if the crack initiates from the notch. Fracture surfaces of the specimens after thermal shock testing and also fracture toughness testing are examined by scanning electron microscope (SEM).

Thermal shock fracture toughness is given by the following thermal shock test results. Based on the elastic stress analysis and linear fracture mechanics, the stress intensity factor K_I at the notch tip of the thermal shock testing specimen can be assumed at the next equation [6,7].

$$K_I = \frac{\alpha E \sqrt{R} \Delta T}{1 - \nu} \cdot \frac{2.24}{\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{c}{R}} \cdot \int_0^R \frac{\sigma_\theta^*}{\sqrt{c^2 - \xi^2}} d\xi \quad \dots (2)$$

Fig.1 The notched disk type specimen for thermal shock test.

Where α is coefficient of thermal expansion, E is elastic modulus, R is radius of specimen, ΔT is temperature difference of thermal shock, ν is Poisson's ratio, ξ is length along the notch and σ_{θ}^* is nondimensional tangential thermal stress obtained in uncracked disk respectively. Therefore,

$$K_I = \frac{\alpha E \sqrt{R} \Delta T}{1-\nu} K_I^* \quad \dots (3)$$

where K_I^* is nondimensional stress intensity factor, which is function of c/R , τ (Fourier number) and β (Biot number). K_I^* shows maximum value as the function of only β . When the specimen with an arbitrary notch length subjected thermal shock shows crack propagation with the minimum temperature difference ΔT_c at this critical condition, stress intensity factor K_I in eq.(3) represents thermal shock fracture toughness $(K_{Ic})_{\text{thermal}}$ as,

$$(K_{Ic})_{\text{thermal}} = \frac{\alpha E \sqrt{R} \Delta T_c}{1-\nu} (K_I^*)_{\text{max}} \quad \dots (4)$$

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

(a) Thermal Shock Resistance

In all thermal shock test of particulate filled composites, test results shows the same tendencies as those obtained in neat epoxies [2,6]. Fig.2 shows one of the example of these results. This figure presents thermal shock resistance of spherical alumina particulate 120 phr filled resin as a function of normalized notch length. The thermal shock resistance is defined as the critical temperature difference; ΔT_c , which corresponded to the least temperature difference to initiate the crack from the notch. This critical temperature difference is clearly observed and decrease with increasing notch length, and takes a minimum value at $c/R = 0.2$. This minimum critical temperature difference at $c/R = 0.2$ can be used to evaluate the thermal shock resistance.

The effects of filler content on thermal shock resistance at $c/R = 0.2$ is classified into three groups as shown in Fig.3. The thermal shock resistance of hard particulate filled composites, such as SiC and Si₃N₄, increase rapidly with an increase of filler contents (a). That of silica and glass beads filled composites also increase but only gradually (b). While, that of both angular and spherical alumina filled composites show decreasing tendency with filler content (c).

Fig.2 Thermal shock test result of spherical alumina particulate 120 phr filled composites.

Fig.3 Effect of filler contents on thermal shock resistance at $c/R = 0.2$.
(a): Si_3N_4 , (b): SiO_2 , (c): Al_2O_3 .

Generally the strength of particulate/ matrix resin interface of alumina filled composite is weak. In order to investigate the influence of the interface bonding strength on thermal shock resistance, thermal shock test result of silane finished alumina filled composite is compared with that of same particulate without any surface treatment, as shown in Fig.4. Interface modified alumina filled composite shows almost the same thermal shock resistance as neat resin ($V_f = 0$), especially at high filler content. The interface bonding strength is very important factor determining the thermal shock resistance.

Fig.4 Effect of surface treatment on the relation between thermal shock resistance of spherical alumina particulate filled composite.

	crack propagates	crack doesn't propagate
without surface treatment	○	●
silane finished	△	▲

(b) Fractography

Fracture surfaces after thermal shock test and fracture toughness test are observed by SEM [7]. At lower particulate content, all fracture surfaces show similar appearance, i.e. smooth surface with no evidences of particulate. But at higher filler content, following characteristics are recognized.

Except of the alumina filled composites, fracture surfaces after thermal shock test and fracture toughness test showed the same morphology. In the case of strong particulate such as SiC or Si₃N₄, rough fracture surfaces are observed. The detailed observation confirmed that thin resin layers are remained on the particulate surface. In the case of weak particulate such as SiO₂ or glass beads, flat surfaces with fractured particulate are observed.

On the other hand, in both angular and spherical alumina particulates, different surfaces are observed in thermal shocked and fracture toughness tested specimens. Fracture surface after thermal shock test shows obvious debonded interface, while in the surface after fracture toughness test interface debonding is not recognized. Then the crack in alumina filled composite seems to be easy to propagate with the interface debonding as a result of thermal shocking.

Fracture surface of silane finished alumina filled composite after thermal shock test is compared with that of same particulate with no surface treatment as shown in Fig.5. Since resin layers can be observed obviously on the particle surface, silane finished composite seems to have good adhesion (a). On the other hand, bare alumina particle is observed on the fracture surface of unmodified composite (b).

Fig.5 SEM observations of fracture surface of spherical Al_2O_3 filled composites after thermal shock test. (a) ; finished with silane coupling agent , (b) ; without surface treatment.

FEM ANALYSIS

Only in the case of weak interface particulate such as alumina, debonding on the particle/ matrix interface is recognized. Noticing the negative effect of filler content on thermal shock resistance, the crack propagation behavior in the presence of debonding at the particulate interface is investigated. In order to discuss the crack propagation behavior of weak interface particulate filled composites under thermal shock condition, stress field on crack tip is analyzed with finite element method. MSC / PATRAN, FEA & THERMAL (The Macneal-Schwendler Co.) is used for this numerical analysis. The model for this analysis is the notched disk type specimen used in thermal shock test.

FEM analysis is performed by two steps. First, temperature and stress distribution of hole disk specimen are calculated assuming uniform material. Then, for second step, using the result of first step calculation as boundary condition, small region near crack tip containing two particles is analyzed. The small region for this FEM model is $100 \times 100 \mu\text{m}$ square plane including crack tip in the center and two particles at the opposite side of the crack tip unsymmetrically as shown in Fig.6. Where the particle diameter $d = 9 \mu\text{m}$ which is mean diameter of spherical alumina particulate, the distance of the particles $\lambda = 1.1 d$, and the other dimensions are $l = (\lambda + d)/2$, $a:b = 1 : 3$. The interfaces of the two particles are assumed to have perfect adhesion or debonded completely

Fig.6 FEM model of the notch tip region for crack propagation analysis.

In this study, the crack propagation direction is estimated by strain distribution and K value which proposed by Yamazaki *et.al.* [8]. The crack will propagate in the direction of high K value, which has same dimension of the stress intensity factor and is defined as,

$$K = \sigma_{\phi} \sqrt{x} \quad \dots \dots (5)$$

where σ_{ϕ} is tangential stress and x is distance from crack tip.

From the analytical result, in the case of debonded particle exists near crack tip, the crack propagates to the direction of debonded particle even in the case of only farther particle is debonded. While in the case of both particles have perfect adhesion the crack propagates straight between particles. Consequently, if the interface of filled particulate is weakened by thermal shock and debonded is caused on there, crack propagate through the debonded interface preferentially and then fracture toughness obtained under thermal shock condition might be lower than that obtained by general mechanical loading.

EVALUATION OF THERMAL SHOCK FRACTURE TOUGHNESS

The relationship between $(K_{Ic})_{thermal} / (K_{Ic})_{mech}$ and Vf is shown in Fig.7, where $(K_{Ic})_{thermal}$ is thermal shock fracture toughness obtained by eq.(3) with result of thermal shock experiments and $(K_{Ic})_{mech}$ is general fracture toughness obtained by 3-point test with SEN specimen. It can be seen that the thermal shock fracture toughness of composites filled with well bonded particulates is almost the same as general value or larger than unity. On the other hand, the ratio for the composites filled with weak bonded particulates, such as alumina, decrease with increasing Vf.

Because the relation of $(K_{Ic})_{thermal} / (K_{Ic})_{mech} < 1$ in the alumina composites means that the fracture toughness under thermal shock condition is overestimated by general fracture toughness, evaluation of the composites is examined in detail. As mentioned previously, the interface debonding is observed only in thermal shock test specimen. Therefore, for the evaluation of thermal shock fracture toughness, K_{Ic} should be measured under the condition in which same debonding is expected as of thermal shock test. For the purpose of this measurement, the fracture toughness test with using pre-thermally shocked SEN specimen is examined.

From the surface observation in SEM of this pre-thermally shocked specimen, debonding is able to be observed, i.e. fracture mechanism is recognized almost the same as that of thermal shock test, while it is not detected except alumina filled composite. The fracture toughness measured by the pre-thermally shocked specimen; $(K_{Ic})_{pre-thermal}$ is compared with $(K_{Ic})_{mech}$ and $(K_{Ic})_{thermal}$ in Table 1. The modified value of the fracture toughness, as a result of pre-thermally shocked specimen, is close to thermal shock fracture resistance a little.

Table 1 The comparison of $(K_{Ic})_{mech}$, $(K_{Ic})_{thermal}$ and $(K_{Ic})_{pre-thermal}$.

Filler	angular Al ₂ O ₃		spherical Al ₂ O ₃		glass beads	SiC	Si ₃ N ₄
	large*	small*	control	silane			
$(K_{Ic})_{mech}$	1.72	2.30	1.73	1.86	1.65	2.34	2.07
$(K_{Ic})_{thermal}$	1.20	1.50	1.13	1.83	2.10	3.43	2.47
$(K_{Ic})_{pre-thermal}$	1.46	2.05	1.62	1.83	1.66	2.93	2.09

* : Mean diameter of Al₂O₃ particulate (large) 27.3 μm, (small) 3.4 μm.

Fig.7 The relationship between $(K_{Ic})_{thermal} / (K_{Ic})_{mech}$ and V_f .

CONCLUSION

Thermal shock test was conducted on ceramic particulate filled composites. The effect of filler content on thermal shock resistance was shown to be depended on strength of the interface and filled particulate itself. For the composite with weak interface, as alumina filled resin, the thermal shock resistance decreased with increase of volume fraction of the filler. FEM analysis of crack propagation behavior was performed. In the case of debonded particle exists near crack tip, the crack propagates to the debonded particle direction. Thermal shock fracture toughness of these composites were evaluated and compared with general fracture toughness. The thermal shock fracture toughness of composite with weak interface is measured by pre-thermal shocked specimen.

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